

Influence of Creativity and Technology on Academic Performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kano

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Abstract

The study investigates the Influence of Creativity and Technology on Academic Performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education. Two research questions were asked and two null hypotheses were tested for the study. The study used descriptive survey design to guide it. The population of the study consists of all 100 level Business Education Students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education, during the 2023/2024 academic session. A sample size of 135 (65 male and 60 female) was selected using random sampling technique from the target population. The instrument used for data collection is Creativity and Technology of Academic Performance (IOCATOP) Questionnaire designed by the researcher. The instrument was validated by three experts' senior lecturers due to remove all ambiguities of the instrument for the respondents. Pilot study was carried out at Federal College of Education Kano using thirty (30) 100 level business education students. The reliability coefficient of the instrument obtained was 0.87. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The regression analysis was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of this research reveal that there is significant influence of creativity on academic performance among Business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kumbotso Kano State Nigeria (P-value, 0.000). The recommendations were made as creativity should be used by the lecturers while teaching for influencing academic performance among Business education students of Saadatu Rimi university of Education Kano State Nigeria to improve their performance.

Keyword: Business Education Students, Creativity, and Technology of University of Education, in Kano State Nigeria

Introduction

Business education students are students who are enrolled in Business education programmes, primarily at the 100 level in Business Education Department of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Educations Kano State. Business education students must be creative, particularly in connection to creativity and technology, in order to increase their academic performance in learning Business education courses and develop their originality. Students' creativity refers to their ability to apply their ideas to develop product that generates more revenue for the university and society at large. Creativity may be defined as the act of generating new issues of noteworthy ideas that boost the economic ability of an individual, organisation, and the nation at large in order to improve the nation's and the world's productivities (Haruna, 2016). The capacity to think mathematically regarding Business education courses is critical for performing tasks that increase students' productivity in Business education.

In the same vein, Vena et al (2023) stated that the ability to think creatively mathematically is one of the abilities required in the process of learning courses that dealt with mathematics such as Business education in their classroom in order to be functional members of the society where they found themselves for productivities. According to Tabach and Friedlander (2017), students' creative thinking abilities have an influence on students' conceptual understanding abilities during the Business education learning process because students with high creative thinking abilities will apply flexible and creative thinking when solving a problem related to Business education and will not stick to what the lecturers lecture them for technological enhancement of academic performance of Business education students.

Technology refers to a technique that enhances students' performance, skills, and tactics by using technological aspects that simplify and minimise most of the factors that hinder students' poor performance for easy communication of facts in time that allows students to improve their performance. This is consistent with their study's goal of contributing to the existing body of knowledge on successful educational practices and influencing policy choices related to the integration of information and communication technology (ICT) and class management tactics in secondary schools by analysing the interaction that exists between ICT, class size, and academic performance (Olusola et al 2023).

This study is tied to and based on one (1) theory: George Herbert Mead's (George Herbert Mead 1920) Symbolic Interactionism Theory. The theory was chosen because: it deals with the interaction between students' creativity and their skills

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in performing most of the activities that link and display their potentiality, particularly in Business education that deals with creativity and skills in teaching Business education using affecting teaching methods that allows students to interact with their creativity with technology while learning in the class before the time so as to improve their academic performance in Business education.

Symbolic Interactionism Theory:

This theory's perspective is based on the symbolic interaction meaning that people generate and rely on when interacting with two or more people while completing activities. Although symbolic interactionism derives from Max Weber's argument that individuals act according to their creativity, technology, and interpretation of the meaning of their reality, it was brought to American sociology in the 1920s by the American philosopher George Herbert Mead. This is consistent with Korgen and Write (2008), who stated that symbolic interaction theory focused on how people interact in their daily creative lives through symbolic interaction and how they create order and meaning, which led supervisors to correct the students' corrections such as amending, deleting, and editing the activities of answering Business questions those required creativity and technological techniques when performing activities in class and outsidess.

Students Creativity

Creativity relates to the student's imagination, which is displayed particularly while addressing questions that involve the students' thinking abilities. This means that most Business education questions required creativity and critical thinking. Similarly, creative people can design novel solutions to address problems and confront challenges (Ayasrah et al, 2023). They can develop innovative ways to do their assigned responsibilities, solve problems and challenges, and so provide a unique viewpoint to their work (Jarwan, 2013). As a result, this helps organisations and businesses evolve to take a more productive approach (Ayasrah et al, 2023). Employers in this era value creative thinking skills (Majdoubi, 2020; Al-Rubaie, 2020; Nurhamidah et al., 2018). Generally, universities are accused of generating graduates that lack enough talent or expertise in creativity, innovation, and technology (Gube & Lajoie, 2020). As a result, countries, particularly developing and poor ones, and their various related organisations, such as the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Higher Education, should provide a broad space in the educational environment for students to gain and practise creative thinking freely (Ayasrah et al, 2023). Creative thinking is one of the greatest and highest skills and abilities that students at all educational levels should strive for (Akpur, 2020; Gajda, 2016; Safadi, 2015). Creative thinking becomes a life strategy that assists students in developing a thorough awareness of diverse life challenges, allowing them to solve such difficulties in creative and original ways, and adapting to changes in time, knowledge, and technology progress that follow it (Al-Aqbawi, 2019).

Furthermore, it helps to build a variety of human talents and capacities, such as the ability to assess, criticise, link, and apply. Akpur (2020) discovered a link between reflective thinking, creative thinking, and critical thinking in a research of 227 first-year university students in Istanbul, Turkey. Furthermore, all these variables had a beneficial and significant impact on the academic performance of students, particularly Business students. Kim (2020) discovered a positive relationship between engineering students' creativity and academic success. Furthermore, it has been discovered that female students are potentially more creative than male students in executing their activities that deal with courses relating to mathematics, such as Business education. A research of 153 undergraduate students in Malaysian universities found that features of creativity are associated to academic achievement for both male and female students (Ayasrah et al, 2023).

Fatmawati et al. (2019) conducted a study on a sample of 30 students (fourth-semester), Department of Biology Education, IKIP Mtataram, Indonesia, to determine the association between learning performance and each of creative thinking skills and critical thinking skills. It was discovered that there was a link between learning performance and both critical and creative thinking skills. The study found a link between learning performance, critical and creative thinking skills, and student performance (Ayasrah et al, 2023). The relationship between self-perceived creativity and entrepreneurial willingness was studied among 559 Spanish university students (Lagua et al., 2019). Family and academic support for creativity, as well as participation in a creativity course, are major predicting factors of self-perceived creativity. Furthermore, teaching creative content and practice enriches entrepreneurship curricula. To address the growth of students' creativity throughout their university education in order to improve students' performance.

Students' performance refers to their capacity to achieve high grades in a test or examination after lecturers have taught them and given them a test or examination that they pass extremely well. According to Rothstein (2012), student performance refers to a successful completion of performance in a specific subject area of study at a given school by professional lecturers. According to Rothstein (2012), student performance is concerned with students' studies and how they cope with or complete various duties assigned to them by their lecturers throughout the course of a semester or year. Furthermore, Yeboah and Dominic (2014) defined student performance as the ability of pupils to study and remember facts, as well as transmit knowledge

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vocally or on writing. This is consistent with the findings of Norman (2014), who examined the characteristics that contribute to students' success in intermediate Business. Norman wanted to see if factors including students' performance in previous courses, age, gender, and major language of communication influenced Business education students' success. There is a link between having lower class numbers and receiving more individualised attention from teachers, higher levels of student engagement, and increased academic performance (Oyeniran 2014). As a result, doing research on the relationship between the number of students in each class and their performance could produce knowledge regarding the most effective learning environment for kids (Mugure 2020). This means that students should be given greater consideration in terms of learning environment in order to create a conducive environment for effective learning and development of students' performance.

Technology refers to a technique that uses technological aspects to improve students' performance, skills, and tactics by simplifying and reducing most of the factors that impede students' poor performance for easy communication of facts in time that allows students to improve their performance. This is consistent with the study's goal of contributing to the existing body of knowledge on successful educational practices and influencing policy decisions related to the integration of information and communication technology (ICT) and class management tactics in secondary schools by examining the interaction that exists between ICT, class size, and academic performance (Olusola et al 2023). The study's findings have the potential to provide valuable insights and ideas to educators, policymakers, and other stakeholders in Ekiti State and elsewhere.

As a result of the study's findings, secondary school students' experiences teaching and learning science topics will most likely improve (Olusola et al 2023). The impact of the number of students in a scientific class on overall student performance can be advantageous or negative, depending on the settings in the classroom (Kuhlemeier & Hemker 2016). A crowded classroom has a negative impact on both science teaching and student academic performance. When there are more students in a school, there are also more pupils in each class, which may cause issues with the students' performance. According to Olusola et al. (2023), class size has evolved into a phenomenon that is widely cited in educational literature as having an impact on student feelings and successes, as well as school administration, quality, and finances. According to him, the number of pupils in a class is almost usually chosen by administrators, and teachers have little or no influence in the matter.

Students' performance in science disciplines has been seen to be declining in Ekiti State over the years, according to researchers (Olofin & Kolawole 2020). Many arguments have been advanced in the literature for students' low performance, but it appears that little focus has been placed on pupils learning through ICT/internet facilities and conducive class-size. The researchers discovered that academic achievement of students in science disciplines has been declining in Ekiti State over the years. The study's participants are specifically secondary school students engaged in science programmes in the Nigerian state of Ekiti. Science classes are critical for developing scientific literacy, preparing students for future education, and preparing them for potential careers in science-related fields. Learning how information and communication technology (ICT) and the number of students in a class affect academic achievement in different courses has the potential to improve scientific education in the field (Olusola et al 2023). Based on this premise, the study studied the effects of ICT/internet facilities and class size on the academic achievement of secondary school students in science subjects.

Business education has been discussed by various authors who shared the same worldview based on their definitions. Business education is a process in which data relating to an organization's economic activities are measured, recorded, and disseminated to interested parties for the goal of analysis and interpretation in order to make proper Business decisions (Abdullahi, 2016). It informs owners/managers and other Business stakeholders about what is going on in the system. Business education informs a wide range of interested parties and eventually demonstrates how a Business has been managed over time-whether successfully or unsuccessfully. Business education also gives information about a firm's financial status as of the deadline for making decisions using skills, as well as to guide gender and increase student performance (Okoye, Uniamikogbo, & Adeusi, 2017).

According to the Business Education Change Committee (BECC), Business educators should focus on: businesses' organisational knowledge; Business systems must give information that represents the entire scenario. Unstructured problems: Because Business problems are generally unstructured, boosting candidates' analytical and analytical ability is more important than memorising. Another thing to notice is the increased emphasis on integrating active learning into pedagogy and technology across the Business curriculum. He also complained about the gap between the requirements of the real sector and the subjects taught in Business courses. He remarked that Business enrolment and attraction were declining, and Business academicians were dissatisfied (Yilmaz, 2022). Accountants must be able to use professional judgement and be skeptical. Business competencies are seen to need to work in tandem with management competencies. Worked up the Business education framework that allows students to have more understanding for handling Business in any situation (Yilmaz 2022).

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Students' performance has been identified as an important issue for tertiary institutions, and research into the possibility of students' performance is also important for universities of education, their lecturers, and students, and can be effective in making policy on students' admission programme and changes in teaching method to improve students' performance while teaching Business education. Measuring students' performance in learning Business education at universities of education based on internal and external factors such as students' ability, interest, language speaking, background level as well as conducive atmosphere, sophisticated learning materials especially those related to Business education, the research attempts to identify and combine the most important factors while also highlighting the important results for selecting the most qualified candidates and, as a result, avoiding Business students' failure and drop-out (Velasco, 2021).

For the purpose of this study, below were considered as the empirical studies of the research: Ayasrah et al (2023) conducted a study titled "Practicing Creative Thinking and its relation to academic performance among students of the Jordan University of Science and Technology. Three (3) objectives were raised as well as three (3) null hypotheses were tested for the study. One thousand and one hundred and fifty-nine (1159) Students of the university in the faculty served as the sample sizes of the study. The results of the study indicated that students of Jordan University of Science and Technology are practicing creative thinking at a moderate level reaching 2.96 at Likert scale. Moreover, it revealed that there is a statistically significant difference in the level of practicing creative thinking due to gender favouring male students. A close relationship between the level of practicing creative thing and academic achievement was found, where 20% of the research sample having high academic achievement showed moderate level of practicing creative thinking.

This research work is similar in context with the previous because they both concentrated on the use of a creativity of the performance of Students. Both studies considered the participation of the students in the teaching process as of paramount importance for the study. The previous research work is relevant to the present study because it helped in the literature development. Despite their similarities, these research works differ to the extent that the previous research work was carried out at Jordan University of Science and Technology but the present work was conducted at Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kano, Nigeria. Hence, they differ in location. The previous study raised and tested only three (3) objectives, and three (3) null hypotheses in order to guide it. The present study raised and tested two (2) specific objectives null hypotheses for the study. The previous study did not specify the population used for the study. The present study does so. The previous study did not specify the statistical tools used in testing the null hypothesis, which is better to be identified for the help of the reader(s) in determining the reliability of the instrument of the statistical tools used to guide it.

Olusola et al, (2023) conducted a study, titled "Impact of ICT and Class Size on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Science Subject in Ekiti State". The study tested two null hypotheses in order to guide the study. The design used for the study were descriptive survey and ex-post-facto designs. The sample sizes of the study include 110 science teachers and 2444 students whose secondary schools were used. The students were selected using multistage sampling techniques. The data of the study were analysed using Pearson Products Moment Correlation Coefficients. The result showed that there was significant relationship between availability of ICT and academic performance in schools. The study also revealed that there is significant relationship between class-size and academic.

This research work is similar in context with the previous research work because they both concentrated on technology on students' performance. In the previous study used Pearson Products Moment Correlation Coefficient to test the null hypotheses. While the present study used regression analysis to test the null hypothesis 1 and 2, in order to determine the influence of nexus creativity on performance of Business education at Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kumbotso Kano State. The previous research work is relevant to the present study because it helped in the literature development. Despite their similarities, these research works differ to the extent that the previous research work was carried out at Ekiti State Nigeria, but the present work was conducted at Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kumbotso Kano State. Hence, they differ in location. The previous study tested only two (2) null hypotheses in order to guide it. The present study raised and tested two (2) null hypotheses. The previous study did not use proper statistical tools in determining the reliability coefficient of the instruments. This means that t-test is not supposed to be used in determining the reliability of the instrument. The previous study did not explain where the study used the two designs appropriately for the readers to be educated.

In a global competition for job specification and the placement of students appropriately, their performances have been identified as an essential determinant ingredient for providing students with more career opportunities, choices and job security. This is in line with the position of Mamman (2016) who stated that students' performances are the ingredients of students' enhancement and societal development to minimise poor performance of students. This is in line with the position of Bayram-Jacobs and Hayirsever (2016) who stated that neglecting students-centre while teaching increases the poor performance of students that are in line with the reasons that necessitated the conducting of this study from the researcher's assessment on the

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declining of students' performance in universities of education. In confirmation of the above-mentioned statement, the researcher's assessment of the recent performance of Business education students from their semesters results between 2019 and 2023 revealed that students' performances were very poor and declining. These poor performances of students agree with the position of Enwere and Enwere (2014) as well as Obidile, Amobi, Uzoekwe and Akuezilo (2017) that the major reasons for poor performance of students was neglecting students' creativity and technology while teaching students Business education. Most of the lecturers did not allow the students to participate fully in the process of answering questions. If the creativity and technology were not considered in teaching Business education the students' performance would not be improved.

Objectives of the study:

The following served as the objectives of this study:

1. Examine the influence of creativity on academic performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria.
2. Determine the influence of technology on academic performance of Business Education students at Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria, Nigeria.

Research Questions:

The following research questions were answered for the study

1. What is the influence of creativity on academic performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria?
2. What is the influence of technology on academic performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

In line with the research questions of the study, the following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance on this study:

1. Creativity has no significant influence on academic performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria
2. Technology has no significant influence on academic performance among Business education students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria.

Methodology

This paper used descriptive survey design to source the data using the opinion of the students with the help of structure questionnaire among the population of the study. The population of the study was made up of one hundred and thirty-five (135) 100 level Business education students in Business Education Department of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education, Kumbotso Kano State Nigeria. Based on the nature of the population and the topic, all students served as sample size of the study. Random sampling technique was used in selecting the sample sizes of the study. *Influence of Creativity and Technology of Performance (IOCATOP) Questionnaire* with five items each which were designed by the researcher and served as an instrument for data collection. The respondents' responses of the copies of questionnaire were rated using four scales. The scales are Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree which was analysed using the mean and standard deviation and regression analysis.

The instrument was validated by three experts' senior lecturers before carrying out the pilot study. The pilot study was conducted using (30) respondents such as twenty-one (21) male and (09) nine female Business education students at Federal College of Education Kano using degree 100 level students who are nearest to the population of the study. They have the same features with the population of the study. The result of the pilot study splits into two using split half test and tested the reliability using SPSS by Cronbach Alpha and derived the reliability coefficient of 0.87. The researcher administered the instruments to the students and retrieved back. Ninety-seven (97) copies of the questionnaire was collected back and analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics such as mean and standard deviation and regression analysis. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance, if the P-value is equal or greater than the Alpha value ($0.05 \geq$), then the null hypothesis is accepted and concluded that there is no significant influence between the variables when the P-value is less than the Alpha then the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is significant effect between the variables.

Results

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Research Question One: What is the influence of creativity on academic performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria?

A questionnaire result was used to answer this research question, and shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Mean and Standard Deviation on the Influence of Creativity on Academic Performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria.

Saadatu Rimi University of Education Business Education Students	N	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
Influence of Creative	97	22.52	12.62	3.7
Academic Performance	97	18.82	1.99	

Source (Field Survey, 2024)

Table 1 shows that the mean in the Influence of creativity mean was 16.52 and the standard deviation was 2.62 ($\chi = 16.52$; $SD = 2.62$), whereas the academic performance of business education students mean was 18.82 and the standard deviation was 1.99 ($\chi = 18.82$; $SD = 1.99$). The respondents at the influence of creativity on the academic performance among business education students of Saadatu Rimi University of Education Kano State had a mean difference of 3.7

Research Question Two: What is the influence of technology on academic performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria?

A questionnaire result was used to answer this research question, and shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Mean and Standard Deviation on the Influence of Technology on Academic Performance among Business Education Students of Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria.

Saadatu Rimi University of Education Business Education Students	N	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
Influence of Technology	97	23.87	13.73	5,10
Academic Performance	97	18.82	1.99	

Source (Field Survey, 2024)

Table 2 shows that the mean in the Influence of technology mean was 23.87 and the standard deviation was 13.73 ($\chi = 23.87$; $SD = 13.73$), whereas the academic performance of business education students mean was 18.82 and the standard deviation was 1.99 ($\chi = 18.82$; $SD = 1.99$). The respondents at the influence of technology on the academic performance among business education students of Saadatu Rimi University of Education Kano State had a mean difference of 5.10.

Null Hypothesis One: Creativity has no influence on the performance of Business education students in Sa'adatu Rimi of Education, Kano in Nigeria

Data collected to address the null hypothesis one was summarised in Table 3

Table 3 Summary of Regression Analysis on the Creativity of Significant Influence of Performance of Business Education Students at Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sign
Creativity	(4.467)	2.624	(2.803)	.727	.578	.460	0.000
Students' Performance	13.637	5.910	2.538				

Source: Field survey 2024 $P > 0.05$

The regression analysis on Table 3 was to determine the influence of creativity of students' performance in Business education at Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kumbotso. The result revealed a constant Beta value of (4.467) (Nexus Creativity) with the t-value of (2.803) against the coefficient value of 2.538 (Students' Performance) and t-value of 4.467. The R-value was .727 with R²-value of .578 and Adjusted-r of .460 with a p-value of 0.000. The result indicated that nexus creativity on students' performance of Business education with a variance of 58% ($r^2 .578 \times 100$). This means that for each single increase

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on influence of creativity, there was an increase of students' performance in Business education of 58%. The observed=0.000 was less than the α value (0.05) indicating a significant influence of nexus creativity of students' performance. This implies that the influence of nexus creativity of students' performance in Business education was rejected and concluded there is significant influence of nexus creativity on students' performance in Business education at Sa'adatu Rimi university of education Kumbotso Kano State Nigeria.

Null Hypothesis Two: Technology has no influence on the performance of Business education students in Sa'adatu Rimi of Education, Kano in Nigeria

Data collected to address the null hypothesis one was summarised in Table 4

Table 4 Summary of Regression Analysis on the Technology of Significant Influence of Performance of Business Education Students at Sa'adatu University of Education Kano, Nigeria

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sign
Technology	(5.567)	2.725	(3465)	.778	.678	.477	0.000
Students' Performance	14.657	5.945	2.579				

Source: Field survey 2024 P>0.05

The regression analysis on Table 4 was to determine the influence of technology of students' performance in Business education at Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kumbotso. The result revealed a constant Beta value of (5.567) (Nexus Technology) with the t-value of (2.725) against the coefficient value of 2.579 (Students' Performance) and t-value of 5.945. The R-value was .778 with R²-value of .678 and Adjusted-r of .477 with a p-value of 0.000. The result indicated that creativity on students' performance of Business education with a variance of 68% ($r^2 .678 \times 100$). This means that for each single increase on influence of technology, there was an increase of students' performance in Business education of 68%. The observed=0.000 was less than the value (0.05) indicating a significant influence of nexus technology of students' performance. This implies that the influence of technology of students' performance in Business education was rejected and concluded there is significant influence of technology on students' performance in Business education at Sa'adatu Rimi University of education Kumbotso Kano State Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of research question in Table 1 and hypothesis one in Table 3 show that the students who are the opinion on the influence of creativity in Business education agreed significantly that creativity influence the academic performance among of Business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education to improve students' performance in Business education. The findings are consistent with that of Ayasrah et al (2023) who opine the results of the study indicated that students of Jordan University of Science and Technology are practicing creative thinking at a moderate level reaching 2.96 at Likert scale. Moreover, it revealed that there is a statistically significant difference in the level of practicing creative thinking due to gender favouring male students. Akpur (2020) on a total of 227 first year university students, Istanbul, Turkey, showed a positive correlation among reflective thinking, creative thinking, and critical thinking. Moreover, all these parameters affected academic performance of students especially Business education students in a positive and significant way.

Kim (2020) found a positive correlation between the creativity of engineering students and academic performance. In addition, it is found that female students are potentially more creative compared to male students in performing their activity that deal with the course who are related the mathematics such as Business education. A study on 153 undergraduate students in Malaysian universities revealed that aspects of creativity are related to academic performance for both male and female students. The finding related to null hypothesis two in Table 2 revealed the result showed that there was significant relationship between availability of ICT and academic performance in schools. The study also revealed that there is significant relationship between class-size and academic. Mugure (2020) stated that students need to be given more consideration in term of learning environment for students' conducive atmosphere with effective learning and improvement of academic performance of students. This would enable them to perform very well in their learning engagement especially using technologies.

Conclusion

Based on the findings discussed in this study concludes that nexus creativity and technology are the appropriate skills to be used in teaching students Business education at Sa'adatu Rimi university of Education. It is also revealed that nexus creativity and technology help, assist and guide the Business education students to improve their performance regardless of their gender differences. The students who were taught using nexus creativity and technology can earn good grades which will

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enable them to have admission into the postgraduate studies. This will also make their parents proud of their students' performance and the students become productive members of the society after graduation for earning their living.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Creativity should be used by the business education lecturers while teaching for influencing academic performance among Business education students of Saadatu Rimi university of Education Kano State Nigeria to improve their performance.
2. Technology should be used by the business education lecturers while teaching for influencing academic performance among Business education students of Saadatu Rimi university of Education Kano State Nigeria to improve their performance.

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